

Effect Of Curcumin On Hematological , Biochemical And Antioxidants Parameters In *Schistosoma Mansoni* Infected Mice

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Abstract: The present study aims to investigate the effect of curcumin on treatment of *schistosoma mansoni* infected mice. Sixty mice were used in this experiment were divided equally into four groups ,the first kept as control, the second supplemented with curcumin , the third infected with *schistosoma mansoni* and the fourth infected and treated with curcumin. Our results emphasized on the presence of anemia, leucopenia , neutropenia and eosinophilia in infected groups either treated or non-treated with an improvement in the treated group. The biochemical parameters; ALT, AST, ALP, total protein, albumin, AFP, TNF- α and lipid profile (TC, TG, HDL-C & LDL-C) improved significantly in infected treated mice compared with infected one. By the same way, results showed an improvement of some anti-oxidant parameters (MAD, GSH, CAT and SOD) in *Schistosoma mansoni* infected treated mice.

Key words: *Schistosoma mansoni*, Curcumin, Erythrocyte, Lucocytes, Liver enzymes, Antioxidant enzymes, Lipid profile.

Introduction

There is no doubt that schistosomiasis is one of the major communicable diseases which affecting human and animals either domestic or wild, as it comes secondly to the malaria with socio-economic and health importance in the developing world (Bergquist & Colley 1998). Schistosomiasis is a chronic debilitating parasitic disease in tropical and subtropical countries caused by *Schistosoma* species (Gryseels *et al.*, 2006). It is affecting about 200 million people infected worldwide and almost 600 million at risk.

There are two types of schistosomiasis: urinary and intestinal schistosomiasis. Four major species are involved in the pathogenesis of Schistosomiasis, three of which, *S. japonicum*, *S. mansoni* and *S. intercalatum*, cause intestinal schistosomiasis, while the fourth, *S. haematobium*, causes urinary Schistosomiasis (Sekou *et al.*, 2006).

Schistosoma is still one of the most prevalent epidemic disease in Egypt and in other developing countries in spite of many attempts to control this parasitic infection over many years (El-Khoby *et al.*, 2000). Schistosomiasis mostly affecting the liver and intestine causing granuloma formation, fibrosis and

certain necrotic changes in the hepatic tissues (Elbanhawey *et al.*, 2007)

Current treatment relies on praziquantel (PZQ) (Zhang & Coultas 2013), The drugs of choice for treatment of schistosomiasis which was developed in the late 1970s (Seubert *et al.*, 1977). However, praziquantel does not treat early infection or prevent reinfection (Magnussen, 2003). In addition to, Numerous evidences indicates to increasing the emergence of strains of *Schistosoma mansoni* resistant to praziquantel (Melman *et al.*, 2009, Van der Werf, 2003 and Zhang & Coultas 2013).

In the last few years, there is an obvious increase in searching for antiparasitic drugs from natural sources, especially from plants, which are the main source of biologically active compounds for the development of new treatments (Magalhães *et al.*, 2009 and Silva *et al.*, 2009). One of these compounds is curcumin.

Curcumin is a yellow pigment from rhizomatous plant turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions throughout the world, (Cerny *et al.* 2011). Curcumin is widely used as a spice and coloring agent in several foods such as curry, mustard and potato chips as well as cosmetics

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and drugs (Okada *et al.*, 2001 and Joe *et al.*, 2004). Extensive in vitro and in vivo studies have indicated that curcumin has a potent antitumor, anti-viral, anti-oxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties (Aggarwal & Harikumar, 2009 and Tu *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, several recent reports showed that curcumin exerts beneficial effects in animal models of liver toxicity, inflammation and cirrhosis (Chen & Zheng, 2008 and Fu *et al.*, 2008).

Several reports revealed that curcumin enhances the hepatic detoxification by acting as a free radical scavenger, increases the glutathione/glutathione disulfide ratio to reduce oxidative stress and inhibits the activation and nuclear translocation of nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) (Leclercq *et al.*, 2004 and Reyes-Gordillo *et al.*, 2007). Recent study postulated that curcumin protects against hepatic fibrosis by inactivating Hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) through activation of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ , which interrupts platelet-derived growth factor and epidermal growth factor signaling in activated HSCs, (Lin & Chen, 2008).

Moreover, the use of curcumin as parasitocidal agents has been extensively studied. It has an activity against *Leishmania* (Koide *et al.*, 2002 and Das *et al.*, 2008), *Giardia lamblia* (Perez-Arriaga *et al.*, 2006) and *Trypanosoma* (Nagajyothi *et al.*, 2012). The first studies about the curcumin effects on *Schistosoma mansoni* showed the schistosomicidal effect of the oil extract of *C. longa* against *S. mansoni* infected mice (El-Ansary *et al.*, 2007). Morias *et al.*, (2013) and Allam (2009) described in vitro and in vivo Schistosomicidal activity of curcumin against *S. mansoni* adult worms. Recently, El-Agamy *et al.*, (2011) showed that curcumin has a potent anti-fibrotic activity in suppressing and reversing *S. mansoni*-induced liver fibrosis.

On the basis of anti-protozoal and anti-parasitic activity of medicinal plants and natural products, the aim of the present work was to evaluate the antishistosomal activity of curcumin against *Shistosoma mansoni*.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals

All common chemicals used were purchased from one of the following suppliers Sigma Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA). All other chemicals and reagents were of the highest purity commercially available and were purchased from the British Drug Houses (BHD), Poole Dorset, UK. The diagnostic kits are purchased

from Human Company (Germany).

Experimental animals

Sixty male CD-1 Swiss albino mice (8-10 weeks of age) used throughout the present study. Thirty mice infected with eighty *Schistoma mansoni* cercariae. The experimental animals were purchased from Theodore Bilharz Research Institute (TBRI, Imbaba, Giza, Egypt). All animals were maintained on standard commercial diet and water ad libitum.

Experimental design:

Animals were divided into four groups with 15 mice in each group, as the following:

Group I: healthy control group received normal diet (non-infected non-treated).

Group II: healthy received normal diet mixed with curcumin (600 mg/kg/diet) (non-infected treated) from the 15th day after receiving the animals and continue for 6 weeks.

Group III: infected and received normal diet (infected non-treated).

Group IV: infected and received normal diet mixed with curcumin (600 mg/kg/diet) (infected treated) from the 15th day after receiving the animals and continue for 6 weeks.

Five animals from each group were sacrificed for sampling at the 2nd, 4th and 6th week post treatment.

Hematological examination:

Whole blood samples were collected from retro-orbital venous plexus of mice in EDTA tube for determination of erythrocytic count (RBCs), haemoglobin concentration (Hb), haematocrit value (PCV), mean cell volume (MCV), mean cell haemoglobin (MHC), mean cell hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), total (TLC) and differential leucocytic count according to Feldman *et al.*, (2000).

Biochemical Analysis

Serum and liver homogenate were taken for all measurements. Serum samples were collected and stored at -20°C until used. The liver was dissected out, washed in ice-cold saline, blotted dry, and weighed. Then homogenate was prepared in phosphate buffer 0.1M, pH 7.4 and used for the biochemical analysis.

Serum hepatic enzymes

Activities of serum Aspartate transaminase (AST) and Alanine transaminase (ALT) were assessed according to Reitmans & Frankel (1957). alkaline

phosphatase (ALP) was assayed by the kinetic methods of human kits (Germany) according to **EDKC (1972)**. Activities expressed as IU/L. Total protein and albumin were measured according to **Doumas et al., (1981)**. Serum globulin was calculated by subtracting the obtained albumin value from the total protein as described by **Doumas & Biggs (1972)**. Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and Alfa-fetoprotein were assayed using a commercial ELISA kit.

Estimation of serum lipids

Total cholesterol (TC), Triglycerides (TG) and high density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) were measured according to **Richmond (1973)**, **Wahlefeld & Bergmeyer (1974)**, **Warnik et al., (1983)** respectively by the human kits (Germany). Low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) was estimated by the formula of **Friedewald et al., (1972)**.

$LDL-C = (\text{total cholesterol}) - (\text{HDL-C}) - (\text{triglycerides}/5)$

Estimation of lipid peroxidation

Quantitative estimation of lipid peroxidation was done by determining the concentration of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) in serum and liver tissue homogenates by the method of **Ohkawa et al., (1987)**. The amount of malondialdehyde (MDA) formed was quantified by reaction with TBARS and used as an index of lipid peroxidation. The results were expressed as nmol of MDA/g of wet tissue using a molar extinction coefficient of the chromophore ($1.56 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M/cm}$) and 1, 1, 3, 3-tetraethoxypropane as standard.

Determination of non-enzymatic antioxidants

Reduced GSH was determined according to the method of **Ellman (1959)** based on the formation of a yellow coloured complex with Ellman's reagent (0.0198% DTNB in 1% sodium citrate). The color developed was read at 412 nm.

Assay of antioxidants enzymes

Superoxide dismutase was assayed spectrophotometrically according to **Paoletti and Mocali (1990)**. This method consists of purely chemical reaction sequence that generates superoxide from molecular oxygen in the presence of EDTA, manganese chloride and mercapto-ethanol. NAD(P)H oxidation is linked to the availability of superoxide anions in the medium. The decrease in absorbance was monitored at 340 nm, One unit of SOD activity is defined as the amount of enzyme required to inhibit

the rate of NAD(P)H oxidation of the control by 50%. Catalase assay was carried out according to the method of **Aebi (1974)**. One unit was defined as that amount of the enzyme which converts one mole substrate to product in one second.

Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error (S.E.). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was first carried out to test for any differences between the mean values of all groups. If differences between groups were established, the values of the treated groups were compared with those of the control group by a multiple comparison t-test. A value of $p < 0.05$ was interpreted as statistically significant (**Tamhane & Dunlop (2000)**).

Results and Discussion

The erythrogram, in the present work, showed microcytic hypochromic anemia in infected non-treated and infected treated group all over the experimental periods (Table 1). This sign marked from a significant decrease in all of the erythrocytic parameters (the mean values of RBCs count, PCV, Hb concentration, MCV, MCH and MCHC) in infected non-treated mice and infected treated group all over the experiment as compared to control group, such decrease was more outstanding in infected non treated group (group III) than infected treated group (group IV). Our results are in agreement with that obtained by **Tjalling et al. (2006)**, **Abd EL-Mottaleb et al., (2008)** and **Nahla et al., (2008)**, who recorded a significant decrease in the erythrocytic count and blood indices accompanied with schistosoma infection. On the contrary our results are disagree with that reported by **Bugarski et al., (2006)** who mentioned insignificant changes in any of the erythrogram parameters. This may be attributed to difference in parasitic species and the dose of parasitic infestation.

Administration of curcumin, to non-infected animal group showed an insignificant change in RBC count as compared to control group. The infected mice treated with curcumin, showed an improvement in erythrogram values (PCV, MCV, MCH and MCHC) as compared to infected non-treated group. **Sharma et al., (2011)** proved that curcumin administration to infected mice improved the erythrocytic count, Hb and blood indices.

Decrease in RBCS count may be returned to the reduction in erythropoiesis in bone marrow and faster rate of destruction of peripheral RBC in spleen (**Coles 1986**). Decrease in Hb can be related to reduction in

size of RBC, impaired biosynthesis of hemoglobin in bone marrow or due to reduction in the rate of formation of RBCs. **Sturrock et al., 1996** attributed the presence of anemia to chronic blood loss that result from the bleeding induced by migration of worms through intestinal wall or due to blood consumption by adult schistosomes .

Table (2) illustrates total (TLC) and differential leukocyte count (Lymphocyte, Neutrophil, Eosinophil and Monocytic count) in control and experimental groups of animals. Both of infected non-treated and infected treated groups showed leucopenia as compared to control group although supplementation of curcumin to non-infected mice improved the WBCs count compared to control group. These results agree with **El-sheikha et al. (2008)** who recorded significant decrease in total leucocytic count in infected mice with Schistosomiasis. In contrast to this result, **Abd EL-Mottaleb et al., (2008)** and **Willingham et al. (1998)** who noticed non-significant change in total leucocytic count in all experimental groups. **Allam 2009** demonstrated that infected treated mice showed insignificant alteration in total leukocytic count.

The difference may be due to difference of infestation dose and or experimental period. Supplementation of curcumin to non-infected mice showed insignificant increase in total leucocytes. These results agree with **Antony et al.1999** who proved that Curcuma longa extract administration increased the total WBC count in Balb/c mice due to its immune-stimulating activity of Curcumin.

On regarding the differential leukocyte count, our results revealed neutropenia, lymphopenia and eosinophilia in either infected non-treated or infected treated groups when compared with control group (Table 2). Similar results were obtained by **Bugarski et al.,(2006)** who reported a significant neutropenia and eosinophilia. Also these results agree with that obtained by **Abd EL-Mottaleb et al., (2008)**, **Sharma et al 2011**, **Vercruyse et al., (1988)** and **Nahla et al. (2008)** who found neutropenia, lymphopenia and eosinophilia accompanied parasitic infection. Simultaneously, a significant neutropenia and lymphopenia were observed, which could be ascribed to the recruitment of these cells to the site of the infection (**Bugarski et al., 2006**). Otherwhile **Abd EL-Mottaleb et al., (2008)** mentioned that the eosinophilia may be due to the powerful defense reaction and allergic manifestation against *Schistosoma mansoni* and their eggs. From the same side, animals were primarily characterized by the

appearance of eosinophilia, which was not unexpected since eosinophilia is the most frequent response to helminths **Klion & Nutman , (2004)**.

Supplementation of curcumin to non-infected mice insignificantly increased neutrophil , eosinophil and lymphocytic count as compared to control group. The results showed insignificant changes of neutrophil, leucocyte and eosinophil in infected treated mice group when compared to infected non-treated group. **Sharma et al, 2011** recorded that curcumin may stabilize the cell membrane and restore various blood variables.

Hepatic damage can affect the metabolic processes in the body due to the role of liver in general metabolism. Enzymes are necessary for normal cellular metabolism including that of the liver (**Rajamanickam & Muthuswamy, 2008**). Hepatoprotective activity of curcumin was evaluated on *Schistosoma mansoni* infected mice by estimation of serum hepatic enzymes. Hepatic cells appear to participate in a variety of enzymatic metabolic activities. Infection of *Schistosoma mansoni* damages the hepatic cells leading to a significant increase in serum levels of AST, ALT ,and ALP respectively (Table 3). The significant ($p < 0.05$) increase of serum AST, ALT, and ALP levels were observed in infected non-treated mice when compared with control group. On the other hand, the infected treated mice (group IV) showed reduction in the serum enzymes level as compared to infected non-treated mice (group III).

These results are in agreement with previously reported by **El-Gowhary et al., (1993)**. **Allam (2009)** reported that, infected mice treated with curcumin restore the hepatic ALT and AST activities that were decreased by *S. mansoni* infection. This amelioration in the activities of liver enzymes could be attributed to the reduction in hepatic granuloma size and fibrosis as well as absence of necrotic hepatic tissue in infected treated mice (**Allam , 2009**). Apparently it appears that the membrane damage seems to be the prime culprit for the marked increase in the serum marker enzymes, AST, ALT, and ALP (**Naik et al., 2011**).

Serum levels of total protein, albumin and globulin were reduced significantly in infected non-treated (group III) as compared to control group (Table 3). However Supplementation of curcumin to infected mice (group IV) resulted in elevation of total protein, albumin and globulin levels compared with infected non treated mice. Similar observations were noticed

by **El-Ansary et al., (2007)** and **El-Emam et al., (2011)**. These results supported through the work of **El-Heig et al., (1977)** who recorded a marked decrease of protein content in *S. mansoni* infected mice.

Alfa-fetoprotein (AFP) is a glycoprotein, of unknown function, normally produced during neonatal development by the liver and in small concentrations by the gastrointestinal tract (**Abelev et al., 1963**). Abnormal serum level of AFP has been reported in patients with liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (**Gupta et al., 2003**). So our work was extended to observe the effect of both *Schistosoma* infection and administration of curcumin on serum alfa-fetoprotein (AFP) and, tumor necrosis factor-alfa (TNF- α) (Table 4). Infected non treated mice showed significant increases of AFP and TNF- α compared with control group. However supplementation of curcumin to infected mice improved the both AFP and TNF- α levels as compared to infected non-treated mice. These results agreed with that observed by **El-Rigal et al, (2011)** , Who recorded elevated level of AFP in sera of *S. mansoni* infected mice which may be considered as an index for liver fibrosis related to Schistosomiasis.

Tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) is a cytokine involved in systemic inflammation and is a member of a group of cytokines that stimulate the acute phase reaction. **Torben & Hailu (2007)** stated that increased level of this inflammatory cytokine after egg excretion may be an indication of its effect in complications of Schistosomiasis, it is capable of inducing tissue injury and fibrosis. The results showed in table (4) indicated that, TNF- α is increased in serum of infected non treated mice compared to control group. The infected mice group treated with curcumin showed an improvement in serum TNF- α level compared with infected non treated mice. These results agree with that obtained by **El-Rigal et al 2011** and **Allam 2009** who observed that infected mice treated with curcumin revealed low serum level tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α).

In order to investigate the hypolipidemic effects of curcumin on *S. mansoni* infected mice, quantitative assay of lipid profile was conducted by measuring the concentrations of serum TC & TG , HDL-C and LDL-C. The infected non treated mice showed increased levels of serum TC &TG and LDL-C as compared to control group (Table 5). There were insignificant differences in HDL-C among all groups.

On the other hand, curcumin supplementation to the infected mice lowered the serum TC &TG and

LDL-C concentrations as compared to infected group. These results are in accordance with that obtained by **Arafa (2005)** while opposite to that reported by **Baum et al., (2007)**. Similar observation were recorded by **Godkar et al., (1996)** who investigated that supplementation of curcumin in diet of Swiss mice caused a marked decrease of serum TC &TG level. The mechanism by which curcumin decreased serum cholesterol in previous study is not known. One hypothesis is that curcumin prevents the increase in serum cholesterol in the animal studies by inhibiting dietary cholesterol absorption (**Arafa, 2005**). Curcumin was reported to cause a little increase of plasma HDL-C in rats (**Arafa , 2005**). Otherwise **Kang & Chen (2009)** provide a novel insights into the roles and mechanisms of curcumin in lowering the level of LDL-C that include curcumin suppressed LDL-R receptor gene expression in activated hepatic stellate cells.

The amount of malondialdehyde (MDA) formed was quantified by the reaction with TBARS and used as an index to lipid peroxidation. Results shown in (Table 6) indicated that MAD level was significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased in serum and liver tissue homogenate of infected non treated mice. However MAD level in serum and hepatic tissue homogenate in infected treated group significantly decreased as compared to that of infected non treated group. The decreased MDA formation in various target tissues following curcumin treatment confirms its anti-oxidant property (**El-Demerdash et al., 2009**). In such types of proliferative process, excessive formation of free radicals occurs, that triggers membrane damage and also augments activation of membrane bound enzymes (**Yadav et al., 2005**). The study applied by (**Naik et al., 2011**) showed that, curcumin treatment inhibited the lipid peroxidation process, which results in decreased MDA formation in edematous and granulomatous, liver, and cardiac tissue.

Reduced glutathione (GSH) are thought to play a vital role in protecting cells against reactive oxygen. During the metabolic action of GSH, its sulfhydryl group becomes oxidized resulting with the formation of corresponding disulfide compound, GSSG. Thus depletion of GSH content is associated with an increase in GSSG concentration resulting with the depletion in GSH/GSSG ratio. The content of reduced glutathione was significantly ($P < 0.05$) decreased in serum and hepatic tissue of infected non treated mice group compared to control group (Table 6). Supplementation of diet with curcumin (group II) caused a significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in the content of reduced glutathione compared with both of

control and infected non-treated groups (group I and group III). Infected mice supplemented with curcumin (group IV) partially restored the content of reduced glutathione to the normal values. Similar protective effect of curcumin pretreatment that showed a powerful antioxidant effect; it notably inhibited MDA production, elevated GSH concentration and attenuated cellular ALT and AST released from hepatocytes reported by **Naik et al., (2004)**. The decreases in GSH level of infected mice is in agreement with the findings of **Leelank & Bansal (1996)**, who reported GSH depletion decreases the GSH/GSSG ratio and production of free radicals. These free radicals interact with membrane lipids leading to the production of lipid hydroperoxides.

Table (6) showed that the activities of serum and liver tissue SOD and CAT of infected non treated mice significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) as compared to control group. Treatment of non-infected mice with curcumin (group II) significantly increased the activities of both serum and liver tissue SOD and CAT as compared to that of infected mice. In addition, a significant recovery relating to serum and liver tissue SOD and CAT was observed in infected mice supplemented curcumin (**El-Demerdash et al., 2009**). Also, **Rizk (1998) and Allam (2009)** reported that catalase activity was enhanced in infected mice treated with curcumin. The antioxidant enzymes superoxide dismutase and catalase play an important role in keeping homeostasis and protection against oxidative damage by removing the toxic free radicals in vivo (**El Shenawy et al., 2008 and Jia et al., 2009**). Recently, **Rizk et al., (2012)** noticed that the reduction in catalase activity could be attributed to its

utilization in scavenging the free radicals overload which generated during Schistosomiasis. A decrease of SOD activity can be resulted from increased removal of superoxide anions (**Sharma et al., 2005**). The levels of antioxidant enzymes are known to be elevated in cells in response to free radical production (**Bandyopadhyay et al., 1999**).

These results coincide with that of **Cerny et al., (2011)** who observed plasma catalase activity as a marker of oxidative stress was 2.4-fold elevated as compared to control and this level further increased to 3-fold following curcumin treatment. **Priyadarsini, (1997) and Masuda et al., (1999)** indicated that the exact mechanism of antioxidant activity of curcumin is not clear, while it is known to react with glutathione and also undergo dimerization by interacting with free radicals. **Naik et al., (2011) and Kurup et al., (2007)** attributed the antioxidant property of curcumin extract to the presence of chemical groups like hydroxyl methoxy and 1,3-diketone conjugated diene system. **Naik et al., (2011)** believed that the antioxidant activity of curcumin might be directly or indirectly associated with the maintenance or preservation of membrane integrity, which might help to prevent the elevation of serum marker enzymes observed during inflammation.

According to our results we concluded that curcumin, could not be used as an anti-parasitic whereas it only improves the alterations of hematological, biochemical ,antioxidants parameters previously induced in *schistosoma mansoni* infected mice.

Table (1) Erythrogram in mice infested with *S. mansoni* and or treated by curcumin (mean ± S.E):

groups parameters		Non infected non treated control	Non infected treated	Infected non treated	Infected treated
2 nd WEEK post treatment	RBCS (X10 ⁶ / UL)	6.56 ±0.05	6.61±0.06	4.74±0.06 ^{ab}	5.21±0.4 ^{ab}
	Hb (g/dl)	12.30±0.07	12.57±0.04	7.44±0.17 ^{ab}	7.30±0.33 ^{ab}
	PCV (%)	41.38±0.06	40.97±0.04	27.01±0.19 ^{ab}	30.90±0.28 ^{ab}
	MCV (fl)	63.13±0.44	61.98±0.61	57.06±0.82 ^{ab}	59.34±0.46 ^{ab}
	MCH (pg)	19.07±0.20	19.03±0.21	15.73±0.45 ^{ab}	14.00±0.55 ^{ab}
	MCHC (gm/dl)	30.21±0.17	30.70±0.08	27.54±0.58 ^{ab}	23.63±1.10 ^{ab}
4 th week post treatment	RBCS (X10 ⁶ / UL)	6.11±0.08	6.09±0.03	4.28±0.05 ^{ab}	4.67±0.03 ^{ab}
	Hb (g/dl)	12.74±0.12	12.53±0.08	7.23±0.07 ^{ab}	7.28±0.15 ^{ab}
	PCV (%)	39.38±0.10	39.03±0.09	25.15±0.20 ^{ab}	27.22±0.23 ^{ab}
	MCV (fl)	64.51±0.67	64.10±0.40	58.72±0.93 ^{ab}	58.37±0.91 ^{ab}
	MCH (pg)	20.87±0.23	20.58±0.13	16.89±0.27 ^{ab}	15.62±0.36 ^{ab}
	MCHC (gm/dl)	32.35±0.29	32.10±0.28	28.76±0.37 ^{ab}	26.75±1.19 ^{ab}
6 th week post treatment	RBCS (X10 ⁶ / UL)	6.23±0.12	6.18±0.02	4.18±0.10 ^{ab}	4.76±0.08 ^{ab}
	Hb (g/dl)	12.91±0.10	12.70±0.18	6.84±0.36 ^{ab}	7.91±0.45 ^{ab}
	PCV (%)	39.95±0.75	39.85±1.03	24.58±0.62 ^{ab}	27.64±0.89 ^{ab}
	MCV (fl)	64.16±0.74	64.47±0.58	58.98±1.40 ^{ab}	58.08±0.62 ^{ab}
	MCH (pg)	20.75±0.32	20.54±0.13	16.43±0.61 ^{ab}	16.63±0.39 ^{ab}
	MCHC (gm/dl)	32.34±0.49	31.88±0.43	27.84±0.72 ^{ab}	28.66±1.12 ^{ab}

a, b, c Significantly difference at P≤ 0.05. a : compared to control, b : compared to non-infected treated. C : compared to infected non treated

Table(2) leukogram in mice infested with *S. mansoni* and or treated by curcumin (mean \pm S.E):

parameters		groups	Non infected non treated control	Non infected treated	Infected non treated	Infected treated
DIFFERENTIAL LEUCOCYTIC COUNT	2 nd week post treatment	TLC (X10 ³ / UL)	8.22 \pm 0.20	8.45 \pm 0.09	6.74 \pm 0.12 ^{ab}	6.72 \pm 0.10 ^{ab}
		LYMPHOCYTE (X10 ³ / UL)	5.19 \pm 0.13	5.22 \pm 0.13	4.41 \pm 0.08 ^{ab}	4.60 \pm 0.14
		NEUTROPHIL (X10 ³ / UL)	2.85 \pm 0.14	3.10 \pm 0.06	1.57 \pm 0.05 ^{ab}	1.69 \pm 0.07 ^{ab}
		ESINOPHIL (X10 ³ / UL)	0.13 \pm 0.01	0.20 \pm 0.01	0.68 \pm 0.02 ^{ab}	0.39 \pm 0.04 ^{ab}
		MONOCYTE (X10 ³ / UL)	0.03 \pm 0.01	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.07 \pm 0.01	0.03 \pm 0.01
	4 th week post treatment	TLC (X10 ³ / UL)	6.80 \pm 0.34	7.18 \pm 0.64	5.40 \pm 0.53 ^{ab}	5.78 \pm 0.36
		LYMPHOCYTE (X10 ³ / UL)	4.84 \pm 0.33	5.09 \pm 0.60	3.11 \pm 0.66 ^{ab}	3.96 \pm 0.69
		NEUTROPHIL (X10 ³ / UL)	1.80 \pm 0.14	1.88 \pm 0.09	1.38 \pm 0.18 ^{ab}	1.34 \pm 0.14 ^{ab}
		ESINOPHIL (X10 ³ / UL)	0.12 \pm 0.01	0.18 \pm 0.08	0.81 \pm 0.07 ^{ab}	0.41 \pm 0.07 ^{abc}
		MONOCYTE (X10 ³ / UL)	0.03 \pm 0.01	0.02 \pm 0.004	0.09 \pm 0.005 ^a	0.07 \pm 0.01
	6 th week post treatment	TLC (X10 ³ / UL)	7.45 \pm 0.23	7.83 \pm 0.43	4.38 \pm 0.50 ^{ab}	4.39 \pm 0.40 ^{abc}
		LYMPHOCYTE (X10 ³ / UL)	5.23 \pm 0.38	5.44 \pm 0.52	2.90 \pm 0.44 ^{ab}	3.18 \pm 0.22 ^{ab}
		NEUTROPHIL (X10 ³ / UL)	2.07 \pm 0.43	2.21 \pm 0.57	0.84 \pm 0.33	0.85 \pm 0.77
		ESINOPHIL (X10 ³ / UL)	0.12 \pm 0.10	0.14 \pm 0.02	0.55 \pm 0.10 ^{ab}	0.31 \pm 0.04 ^{ab}
		MONOCYTE (X10 ³ / UL)	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.09 \pm 0.01 ^{ab}	0.05 \pm 0.01

a, b, c Significantly difference at P \leq 0.05. a : compared to control, b : compared to non-infected treated. C : compared to infected non treated.

Table (3) serum liver enzymes and proteinogram of mice infested with *S. mansoni* and or treated with curcumin (mean \pm S.E):

parameters \ groups		Non infected non treated control	Non infected treated	Infected non treated	Infected treated
2 nd week post treatment	AST (IU/L)	22.41 \pm 0.29	21.36 \pm 0.15	39.66 \pm 0.13 ^{ab}	28.72 \pm 0.25 ^{abc}
	ALT(IU/L)	19.30 \pm 0.62	17.75 \pm 0.35	29.89 \pm 0.63 ^{ab}	22.71 \pm 0.58 ^{abc}
	ALP(IU/L)	38.42 \pm 0.24	37.44 \pm 0.28	58.31 \pm 0.36 ^{ab}	44.32 \pm 0.23 ^{abc}
	Total protein g/dl	6.68 \pm 1.03	6.82 \pm 0.73	3.97 \pm 0.81 ^{ab}	4.01 \pm 0.57 ^{ab}
	Albumin g/dl	2.38 \pm 0.84	2.54 \pm 0.23	1.01 \pm 0.38 ^{ab}	1.42 \pm 0.68 ^{ab}
	globulin g/dl	4.30 \pm 0.19	4.28 \pm 0.50	2.96 \pm 0.73 ^{ab}	2.59 \pm 0.76
4 th week post treatment	AST (IU/L)	34.25 \pm 0.74	36.12 \pm .52	67.00 \pm 0.65 ^{ab}	45.00 \pm 0.92 ^{abc}
	ALT(IU/L)	18.50 \pm 1.36	21.00 \pm 1.2	68.80 \pm 0.5 ^{ab}	32.00 \pm 1.17 ^{abc}
	ALP(IU/L)	35.52 \pm 0.05	32.08 \pm 1.63	72.40 \pm 1.8 ^{ab}	46.47 \pm 0.45 ^{abc}
	Total protein g/dl	6.49 \pm 0.4	6.35 \pm 0.1	4.15 \pm 0.6 ^{ab}	4.87 \pm 0.13 ^{ab}
	albumin g/dl	2.55 \pm 0.5	2.60 \pm 0.8	1.38 \pm 0.14 ^{ab}	1.50 \pm 0.12 ^{ab}
	globulin g/dl	3.94 \pm 0.59	3.75 \pm 0.1.21	2.770.8 ^{ab}	3.37 \pm 0.14
6 th week post treatment	AST (IU/L)	28.00 \pm 1.2	27.14 \pm 0.08	55.00 \pm 0.05 ^{ab}	31.10 \pm 1.02 ^c
	ALT(IU/L)	21.16 \pm 0.9	21.41 \pm 0.19	31.70 \pm 0.06 ^{ab}	22.65 \pm 0.07 ^c
	ALP(IU/L)	36.80 \pm 1.5	38.20 \pm 1.2	67.43 \pm 2.5 ^{ab}	42.25 \pm 1.3 ^c
	Total protein g/dl	5.84 \pm 0.48	5.90 \pm 0.70	3.80 \pm 0.18 ^{ab}	4.52 \pm 0.30 ^a
	albumin g/dl	2.89 \pm 0.21	2.68 \pm 0.83	1.82 \pm 0.5 ^{ab}	2.40 \pm 0.68
	globulin g/dl	2.95 \pm 0.26	3.22 \pm 0.13	1.98 \pm 0.23 ^{ab}	2.12 \pm 0.52

a, b, c Significantly difference at $P \leq 0.05$. a : compared to control, b : compared to non-infected treated. C : compared to infected non treated.

Table (4) serum AFP and TNF of mice infested with *S. mansoni* and /or treated with curcumin (mean ±S.E):

parameters		groups			
		Non infected non treated control	Non infected treated	Infected non treated	Infected treated
2 nd week post treatment	AFP (ng/ml)	7.62±0.10	7.00±0.39	38.65±0.72 ^{ab}	30.12±0.54 ^{abc}
	TNF (Pg/ml)	12.45±0.30	11.48±0.32	33.32±0.50 ^{ab}	24.71±0.27 ^{abc}
4 th week post treatment	AFP (ng/ml)	8.87±0.47	8.51±0.57	50.44±0.70 ^{ab}	41.96±0.23 ^{abc}
	TNF (Pg/ml)	12.35±0.40	10.76±0.37	48.41±0.87 ^{ab}	40.72±1.08 ^{abc}
6 th week post treatment	AFP (ng/ml)	8.94±0.26	8.23±0.54	57.61±0.31 ^{ab}	49.46±0.40 ^{abc}
	TNF (Pg/ml)	11.78±0.64	10.22±0.87	59.87±1.83 ^{ab}	47.71±2.85 ^{abc}

a, b, c Significantly difference at P≤ 0.05. a : compared to control, b : compared to non-infected treated. C : compared to infected non treated.

Table (5) serum lipid profile of mice infested with *S. mansoni* and /or treated with curcumin (mean ±S.E):

parameters		groups			
		Non infected non treated control	Non infected treated	Infected non treated	Infected treated
2 nd week post treatment	Cholesterol (mg/dl)	82.33±0.22	79.83±1.03	111.50±1.97 ^{ab}	96.83±1.72 ^{abc}
	triglycerides(mg/dl)	56.00±0.14	49.70±1.87	77.90±0.57 ^{ab}	65.10±0.16 ^{ab}
	HDL-C (mg/dl)	15.10±0.18	17.60±0.61	14.20±0.78	14.80±1.2
	LDL-C (mg/dl)	56.30±0.04	52.29±0.60	81.72±1.32 ^{ab}	69.01±1.10 ^{ab}
4 th week post treatment	Cholesterol (mg/dl)	85.67±2.16	83.17±0.18	138.83±1.22 ^{ab}	114.33±1.43 ^{abc}
	triglycerides(mg/dl)	48.00±0.20	45.70±0.3	67.12±0.41 ^{ab}	50.39±0.43
	HDL-C (mg/dl)	21.82±1.27	22.48±2.18	19.06±1.16	20.13±1.42
	LDL-C (mg/dl)	54.25±1.54	51.55±1.95	106.35±1.14 ^{ab}	89.12±0.86 ^{ab}
6 th week post treatment	Cholesterol	83.49±2.32	80.57±1.03	104.83±1.72 ^{ab}	99.50±1.87 ^{abc}
	triglycerides(mg/dl)	69.67±0.88	60.35±0.28	92.71±0.37 ^{ab}	89.20±0.81 ^{ab}
	HDL-C (mg/dl)	17.31±0.73	16.91±1.81	15.85±1.38	16.22±0.92
	LDL-C (mg/dl)	52.24±0.24	51.59±0.49	70.47±0.38 ^{ab}	65.44±0.89 ^{ab}

a, b, c Significantly difference at P≤ 0.05. a : compared to control, b : compared to non-infected treated. C : compared to infected non treated

Table (6) levels of GSH, SOD, CAT AND MAD in serum and liver tissue homogenates of (mean ±S.E):

parameters		groups		Non infected non treated control	Non Infected treated	Infected non treated	Infected treated
2 nd week post treatment	GSH	SERUM		12.88±0.22	12.91±0.46	7.26±0.31 ^{ab}	9.70±0.37 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		30.47±0.73	32.60±0.23	13.40±0.18 ^{ab}	24.15±0.95 ^{abc}
	SOD	SERUM		6.94±1.36	7.64±1.43	3.29±0.83 ^{ab}	5.72±1.05 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		23.50±0.61	24.10±0.37	14.25±0.79 ^{ab}	17.70±0.58 ^{ab}
	CAT	SERUM		49.10±6.99	48.31±7.89	31.20±8.56 ^{ab}	36.29±7.33 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		67.80±1.20	70.30±3.42	53.70±3.42 ^{ab}	61.94±3.72 ^{abc}
	MAD	SERUM		0.13±0.2	0.12±0.01	0.62±0.03 ^{ab}	0.39±0.05 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		1.06±0.72	1.00±0.18	1.94±0.15 ^{ab}	1.25±0.11 ^{ab}
4 th week post treatment	GSH	SERUM		14.11±0.95	14.58±0.66	8.62±0.13 ^{ab}	10.73±0.32 ^{ab}
		TISSUE		34.15±0.41	35.78±0.62	18.71±0.30 ^{ab}	25.93±0.43 ^{ab}
	SOD	SERUM		6.10±0.59	6.25±0.23	2.62±0.17 ^{ab}	5.00±0.19 ^c
		TISSUE		21.90±0.61	20.34±0.23	11.84±0.74 ^{ab}	14.69±0.81 ^{ab}
	CAT	SERUM		53.70±7.91	51.30±3.41	23.79±5.87 ^{ab}	40.17±6.58 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		70.32±3.99	72.85±4.86	48.30±5.64 ^{ab}	52.60±8.31 ^{ab}
	MAD	SERUM		0.15±0.40	0.16±0.90	0.87±0.11 ^{ab}	0.30±21 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		0.92±0.30	0.83±0.11	2.16±0.90 ^{ab}	1.72±0.70 ^{abc}
6 th week post treatment	GSH	SERUM		16.80±0.95	18.13±1.2	8.42±1.36 ^{ab}	12.90±1.13 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		33.72±0.93	34.61±0.82	16.32±0.59 ^{ab}	21.80±0.36 ^{abc}
	SOD	SERUM		9.10±0.45	11.30±0.53	6.37±0.31 ^{ab}	8.50±0.39
		TISSUE		25.43±0.16	27.38±0.81	10.93±0.76 ^{ab}	18.47±0.51 ^{ab}
	CAT	SERUM		48.13±3.43	45.19±6.32	32.81±4.37 ^{ab}	36.58±3.45 ^{ab}
		TISSUE		69.28±7.31	71.19±6.39	43.64±8.31 ^{ab}	50.97±4.53 ^{abc}
	MAD	SERUM		0.12±0.31	0.11±0.10	0.46±0.21 ^{ab}	0.32±0.34 ^{abc}
		TISSUE		1.44±0.31	1.55±0.40	2.87±0.82*	1.92±0.48*

a, b, c Significantly difference at P ≤ 0.05. a : compared to control, b : compared to non-infected treated. C : compared to infected non treated. SOD & CAT (U/mg protein in serum & tissue), GSH (mg/dl in serum & nmole/g tissue), MAD (nmole/ml in serum & nmole/g tissue)

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